

SPOT Newsletter

RE-IMAGINING Cultural tourism in Europe

SPOT PROJECT

SOCIAL AND INNOVATIVE PLATFORM ON CULTURAL
TOURISM AND ITS POTENTIAL TOWARDS DEEPENING
EUROPEANISATION

| www.spotprojecth2020.eu |

2022.
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SPOT Newsletter

Dear Reader,

We are pleased to share the third and final newsletter of the EU funded project SPOT, which aims to develop a new approach to understanding and addressing cultural tourism and to promote development of disadvantaged areas on the one side and propose recommendations to areas with tourism overpressure on the other one. The final issue of our newsletter presents research results of the project and our achievements as a partnership. Keep yourself informed about ongoing SPOT activities! Enjoy the reading.

The Editorial team

SPOT AT A GLANCE

SPOT is 3-year EU-funded project under the Horizon 2020 programme, focused on the study of issues related to cultural tourism. The consortium is composed of 15 partners from 14 European countries and Israel. Such a diverse team will bring in a wide range of knowledge, inspirations and ideas including close cooperation with the local, regional or national stakeholders. Cultural tourism has traditionally focused upon visiting “high art” museums and galleries. Our model of cultural tourism by contrast widens the understanding of cultural tourism that more accurately reflects the changing patterns of travel in the 21st century and the newer ways of accessing culture as a result of the digital revolution.

PROJECT NEWS

SPOT WORKSHOPS IN 2022

During 2022 the consortium had four workshops, which focused on specific research questions outlined in the Vision for 2022. The first workshop titled “Good Practices of Cultural Tourism and Tourism Culture” took place on 3 February. Organised by WP1, the workshop centered around five themes, which were discussed in five separate groups: 1. Values of cultural tourism; 2. Cultural changes; 3. Intangible cultural heritage; 4. Creative tourism and 5. Social media and digitalization. The second workshop took place in Ljubljana on 2-3 March. Partners reflected on the results of WP1, discussed Europeanisation and its impact on cultural tourism and reflected on the impact of COVID-19 on Europeanisation and cultural tourism. Discussions resulted in a list of Golden rules for Policy Recommendations, which has been refined during the SPOT consortium meeting in Hermopolis.

The third workshop titled „Cultural tourism and regional development” took place on 5 April in Brno. Partners focused on how can cultural tourism strengthen social cohesion, on what steps have been taken to ensure the economic benefit of cultural tourism, on the main drivers in cultural tourism which contribute to regional and local economic development and on how it can help to sustain and develop local cultures as well as its impact on the environment.

Between May 11th and 13th, SPOT Workshop 4 within WP 2 took place in Romania. Workshop 4 had two parts. One Whole Day Workshop in Bucharest with the participation of all SPOT members in hybrid format (May 11th) and two-days field trip in the IGAR study area (May 12th-13th). During the Whole Day Workshop, a series of issues related to the relationship between cultural tourism and local stakeholders were addressed: What do we want from Stakeholders? What can we offer Stakeholders? How can we help empower local communities? Place Identity and Appreciation of “Otherness”.

The workshop concluded with a meeting at the Buzau County Council where national, regional and local stakeholders discussed with the SPOT project members about the role of stakeholders and researchers/academics in the development and promotion of cultural tourism in the study area.

On June 13-15, 2022, the University of the Aegean team hosted the SPOT consortium meeting on the island of Syros, one of the islands of our UAegean case study. During the first two days of the project meeting (June 13 and 14), the consortium drafted the next steps towards the completion of SPOT project work and deliverables. Specifically, the primary purpose of the meeting was to prepare clear formulations of recommendations to EU stakeholders dealing with Cultural Tourism (CT) for the forthcoming policy roundtable organized by EU officers in Brussels. The meeting also focused on formulating the main messages, recommendations and results of the SPOT project for relevant actors and involved stakeholders at the national, regional and local levels.

Results from the workshops will be published in the Report on Good practices prepared by WP1. The concluding report will contain the following points:

- Good practices and changing in concepts for understanding Cultural Tourism (information from Workshop 1)
- Cultural Tourism and Europeanization (information from Workshop 2)
- Good Practices of cultural tourism as supporting mechanism to local and regional development (information from Workshop 3)
- Good practices of cultural tourism and local engagement (information from Workshop 4)
- Conclusions and recommendations

A collection of Good practices from the case study areas related to cultural tourism development is available in the [Web-based Resource Centre](#).

OUR SERIES OF THEMATIC AND CASE STUDY POLICY BRIEFS

The first series of Policy Briefs have been published in March 2022. The first issue in a series of Policy Briefs present the main findings and practical outcomes of SPOT project. The thematic Policy Briefs provide information and policy-related recommendations for all groups of stakeholders involved in the development of cultural tourism in Europe based on the results of our multi-national study implemented in 15 countries.

The first Policy Brief on „Cultural tourism and Europeanisation” prepared by Wageningen University & Research (WR) team uses the notion of the landscape for broadening the concepts of cultural tourism and Europeanisation and presents recommendations based on that understanding. The Policy Brief is available at [Cultural tourism and Europeanisation](#)

The second Policy Brief by WR team titled „Understanding of Cultural tourism: views of tourists, residents, and entrepreneurs” presents the results of the residential,

business and tourist surveys carried out by the Consortium for European, national and regional stakeholders and advocates for thinking in terms of collaborative structures instead of thinking in target groups. The Policy Brief is available at [Understanding of Cultural tourism: views of tourists, residents, and entrepreneurs](#)

The third Policy Brief „Cultural Tourism from Local Stakeholder’s Perspective” prepared by the team from University of Aberdeen presents the results from a series of stakeholder roundtables organised by SPOT teams. It summarizes the points raised by different stakeholders at a local level and suggests policy directions to deal with their queries. It is aimed at EU level policymakers and national level policymakers as well. The Policy Brief is available at [Cultural Tourism from Local Stakeholder’s Perspective](#)

PolicyBRIEF

www.SPOTprojectH2020.eu

The University of Aberdeen team produced two Policy Briefs focusing on local issues and suggesting a number of improvements based on their findings. The Policy Briefs are available at [The Scottish Borders and Doune](#).

The Policy Brief prepared by Bar-Ilan University introduces the SPOT-IT, a GIS-based innovative tool for the planners, organizers and developers of cultural tourism objects and infrastructures. The Policy Brief provides details about the unique functionality of the tool and its main components. The Policy Brief is available at [SPOT-IT: your smart assistant in the development of cultural tourism objects and infrastructures](#).

The series of Case Study Policy Briefs prepared by the individual teams of the SPOT project focus on specific issues.

Available at <http://www.spotprojecth2020.eu/d2-5>

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Park Güell, an Art Nouveau masterpiece from the Barcelona case study area

SPOT SYMPOSIUM ON THE ISLAND OF SYROS

On June 13-15, 2022, the University of the Aegean team hosted the SPOT consortium meeting on the island of Syros, one of the islands of our UAegean case study. During the first two days of the project meeting (June 13 and 14), the consortium drafted the next steps towards the completion of SPOT project work and deliverables. On the 15th of June, the University of the Aegean team organized a half-day symposium dedicated to the island of Syros and the Cyclades. In the first part of the symposium, the outcomes of SPOT project work undertaken by the University of the Aegean team were presented, followed by a discussion on both the project outcomes and cultural tourism future visions for the case study region. In the second part of the symposium, three invited distinguished scholars on the Cyclades and Syros- Joseph

Stefanou, Professor Emeritus, National Technical University of Athens and Head of the Syros Institute; Kenneth Olwig, Professor Emeritus, Swedish University of Agricultural Sciences; and Martin Engi, Professor Emeritus, University of Bern, participated a round-table panel discussion focused on the island's and the region's culture, history and physical environment. The event was sponsored by SPOT and the Municipality of Syros, and widely publicised in Syros. It was streamlined on YouTube and open to the general public.

BUZĂU LAND WAS DESIGNATED AS UNESCO GLOBAL GEOPARK

The UNESCO Global Geopark label recognizes geological heritage of international significance. Member States unanimously ratified its creation in 2015. The sites of this network present an extraordinary geological diversity that underpins different regions' biological and cultural diversity. The geoparks serve local communities by combining the conservation of their unique geological heritage with public outreach and sustainable development. Among the 8 newly designated UNESCO Global Geoparks is also Buzău Land UNESCO Global Geopark.

UNDERWATER ARCHEOLOGISTS

Hungarian SPOT case study area belongs to the Limes Romanus cultural heritage: two Roman military legion (Brigetio, Azaum) and a military camp with defensive function (Kelemantia) were located here. The two mentioned legions were established in the territory of the former Roman Empire (in the southern part of the Danube river), while the military camp was settled beyond the imperial border (in the northern part of the Danube river). Last year, underwater archaeologists were likely to discover the remains of 4 ancient bridge piers in the Danube river by Kelemantia (near the settlement Izsa), using sonar technology.

SPOT MEETING IN NARVA

On July 29, 2022, SPOT partners from Estonia, Slovenia, Romania and the UK gathered in Narva, the “capital” of the Estonian case study Ida-Virumaa, to explore the 13th century Narva Castle and 19th century Kreenholm district where in the Narva Art Residency they also met with local stakeholders. The debate around Soviet memorials in Estonia was gaining momentum, so the researchers also paid a visit to one of the most controversial of them – Tank T-34 between Narva and seaside Narva-Jõesuu, just across the border with Russia, which has since then been removed.

The findings are supposed to be the remains of a stone bridge between Azaum and Kelemantia and are very unique, because archeologists have still nowhere discovered the remains of a bridge linking the conquered imperial areas with the Barbaricum (latter is located beyond the imperial border). Currently, a lot of questions relates to this theory, therefore, further divings are necessary to prove the assumptions.

SPOT MEETINGS IN HUNGARY/SLOVAKIA AND ISRAEL

In the penultimate week of April, colleagues from Bar Ilan University paid a professional visit to Hungary. As part of their trip, they visited the SPOT case study area of the twin cities of Komárom-Komárno, where they visited cultural tourist attractions such as the fortress system. During their stay they also visited the Hungarian partner, the CERS institute. Following this, Hungarian members of the SPOT project went to Israel in the last week of April. At the same time, Romanian partners of the project came to visit Israel as well and the 3 teams of the consortium took a trip to the case study area of Bar Ilan University, named Beit Shean Valley and the city itself. During the trip, the teams had a meeting with an association of local residents committed to developing tourism in Beit Shean city and the Valley.

ROMAN REMAINS WERE FOUND IN THE DANUBE RIVER BY KELEMANTIA, SLOVAKIA

Hungarian SPOT case study area belongs to the Limes Romanus cultural heritage: two roman military legion (Brigetio, Azaum) and a military camp with defensive function (Kelemantia) were located here. The two mentioned legions were established in the territory of the former Roman Empire (in the southern part of the Danube river), while the military camp was settled beyond the imperial border (in the northern part of the Danube river). Last year, underwater archeologists were likely to discover the remains of 4 ancient bridge piers in the Danube river by Kelemantia (near the settlement Izsa), using sonar technology. The findings are supposed to be the remains of a stone bridge between Azaum and Kelemantia and are very unique, because archeologists have still nowhere discovered the remains of a bridge linking the conquered imperial areas with the Barbaricum (latter is located beyond the imperial border). Currently, a lot of questions relates to this theory, therefore, further divings are necessary to prove the assumptions.

SANT PAU RECINTE MODERNISTA ART NOUVEAU SITE RENEWS THE BIOSPHERE CERTIFICATION IN SUSTAINABLE TOURISM

In July 2022, the Sant Pau Recinte Modernista renewed its commitment to continuous improvement in the management of cultural activities in the Art Nouveau site. In an event attended by representatives of the Barcelona City Council, the Chamber of Commerce, the

Barcelona Provincial Council, the Institute for Responsible Tourism, and hundreds of entities and companies, the Art Nouveau site was certified for the fourth time as part of the Biosphere Sustainable Lifestyle program for tourism.

In 2017, the Institute for Responsible Tourism (ITR) approved the Art Nouveau site for Biosphere Sustainable Tourism certification in recognition of the responsible, environmentally sustainable, socially inclusive and accessible tourism model shaping the management of cultural activities in this pioneering heritage space. The certification is based on the guidelines of the World Charter for Sustainable Tourism and the 17 Sustainable Development Goals of the United Nations' 2030 Agenda.

CONFERENCES AND EVENTS

More information: <http://www.spotprojecth2020.eu/blog>

The contribution of innovative and creative tourism to support sustainable local development - Online event 26 July 2022 - Culture, tourism and people within the European Union Strategy for the Danube Region (EUSDR)

On Tuesday, 26 July 2022, the UNIVR team presented the case study during the on-line workshop entitled The contribution of innovative and creative tourism to support sustainable local development. It was organised and hosted by the Romanian Ministry of Development, Public Works and Administration in the person of Ms Irina Cozma in the frame of Priority Area 3 - Culture, tourism and people within the European Union Strategy for the Danube Region (EUSDR). Invited by the IGAR team colleagues, Giovanna Rech - on behalf of the UNIVR SPOT team - presented their case study discussing The role of international recognitions in local sustainable development. Insights from the UNESCO “effect” in the Italian SPOT case study. This workshop was attended by representatives of several macro-regional strategies of Europe, showing different ways of enhancing the local cultural offer both for citizens and tourists but also several creative modes of coping with troubles due to the pandemics or over-

tourism negative effects. Participants staged a vivid picture and launched a fruitful discussion on innovative ways of supporting sustainable local development in urban or rural areas. It has been a packed opportunity to ensure the visibility of activities within the SPOT project after the participation of the IGAR team in the workshop organised last May. Furthermore, it has been identifying new partners and new project ideas in the European Union cooperation and research strategies.

SPOT team members participated at the Centennial Congress of International Geographical Union (IGU)

The congress took place in Paris between July 18 and July 22 2022. Irit AMIT-COHEN from Israel held a presentation about „The fear of short-term damage to heritage sites and the possibility of converting it into long-term benefits”. Tamás HARDI, Jenő FARKAS, Edit HOYK from Hungary talked about urban sprawl patterns and impacts around Central Europe’s middle-sized cities. Bianca MITRICA, Paul SERBAN, Ines GRIGORESCU, Nicoleta DAMIAN, Irena MOCANU, Monica DUMITRASCU, Cristina DUMITRICA from

from Romania presented findings about „Cultural tourism and rural development based on tourists perception. The showcase of Buzau Carpathians and Subcarpathians”. Małgorzata PSTROCKA-RAK, Sylwia DOŁZBŁASZ, Anna GROCHOWSKA from Poland held a presentation titled „A Shared Vision? Stakeholders' perspectives on the cultural tourism development in the Valley of Palaces and Gardens, Poland”. Irit SHMUEL from Israel presented about „COVID-19 and the transformations in the perception of cultural tourism: The case of Beit She'an Valley, Israel”. Michael SOFER, from Israel presented „The Development Path of the Rural Space in the 21st Century”. Theano S. TERKENLI, Vasiliki GEORGOULA from Greece held a presentation titled „The impact of the COVID-19 pandemic in the Cyclades: balancing between current shortcomings and future regenerative perspectives in cultural tourism”.

SmartCulTour webinar

During the „State-of-the-art in European cultural tourism policies and practices” SmartCulTour webinar on the 20th of June members from the Horizon 2020 SmartCulTour (<http://www.smartcultour.eu/>) and SPOT (<http://www.spotprojecth2020.eu/>) projects discussed cultural tourism policies, responses to Covid-19 and success conditions of different types

of cultural tourism interventions.

After the introduction by the SmartCulTour project coordinator, Bart Neuts (organiser, Department of Earth and Environmental Sciences of KU Leuven) Prof. Claire Wallace (University of Aberdeen) presented findings on the impact of COVID-19 on cultural tourism from the SPOT project. She talked about worldwide changes in patterns of tourism and the possible long-term consequences of the pandemic as well. John Shaddock (University of Aberdeen) presented SPOT findings about policies around cultural tourism, and how these policies are experienced in practice. Simone Moretti (Breda University of Applied Sciences) talked about cultural tourism interventions, with a particular focus on taxonomy, best practices and lessons learnt in the framework of the SmartCulTour project. As a continuation Licia Calvi and Caroline Belt presented best practices, the Brabant Remembers App and the Huesca Living Lab. Following a debate led by Alun Jones (CIHEAM Zaragoza), in the closing remarks Milada Šťastná (Mendel University), coordinator of the SPOT project stressed the importance of cultural tourism policies and that the interconnectedness and communication between stakeholders of different levels is the way we can address identified gaps and progress cultural tourism in the way we think would make it stronger, more resilient and sustainable. To watch the recording of the webinar please visit <http://www.smartcultour.eu/webinar-state-of-the-art/>

Landscapes, wine, literature, and tourism in SPOT. How to connect the dots?

The Special Interest Meeting and Seminar Landscapes, wine, literature, and tourism in SPOT. How to connect the dots? organised by the UNIVR team was held on the 13th-14th September 2022. The scientific discussion aimed to disentangle the multiplicity of connotations of what “cultural” is becoming in the SPOT comprehension of tourism, focussing on the landscape, its products, and its intangible representations. All the SPOT Partners concerned by the theme were invited to illustrate which are the contacts and frictions they have detected in their case studies between the Culture intended as the high culture and the culture intended in its popular, vernacular, folk, ancient, holistic, and other specific modes.

The meeting gathered twenty-seven participants from nine different SPOT Consortium’s institutions. The first day, we discussed the theme from a scientific point of view, while on the second day, we travelled through the UNIVR case study area, appreciating the hills and the literary places of the local writer Beppe Fenoglio visiting a wine cellar where the Barolo wine is produced.

The seminar was inaugurated by prof. Mike Robinson from Nottingham Trent University (UK) with a speech entitled Opening-up Culture for Tourists: Context, Curation and Communication. His presentation explored the ‘opening-up’ of the culture concept for tourists in a post-pandemic world and the ways in which the landscape can act as a narrative thread to anchor and make sense of a variety of activities and experiences. Through several examples from his past and present works, he highlighted the utility value of the real, the symbolic and the imaginary landscape and the creativity of curation that is increasingly

demanded by tourists. In seeking the economic and social development of disadvantaged areas, great importance was committed in communication, translation and ‘re-narrativisation’ as essential practices for connecting with new generations of visitors.

SPOT partners from IGAR, IOER, KRTK, MENDELU, UKF, UAberdeen, UAegean, and Wageningen offered a specific entry to their case studies in Romania, Germany, Hungary, Czech Republic, Slovakia, Scotland, Greece, and the Netherlands from the standpoint of landscape and their unique cultural assets. This has laid the foundations for a more comprehensive understanding of the relation between landscape, cultural tourism representations and practices.

The afternoon was committed to a round table where a part of SPOT Italian case study’s stakeholders was invited to show their experiences of cultural tourism, presenting excellences and key nodes of research and the local management in the UNESCO participatory processes, the cultural sector successes and gaps, and the continuous expansion of the agro-tertiary sector.

University of Ljubljana organizes the final event of the projects MESTUR and SPOT

The final event of both projects took place on 17 June 2022 at the Ljubljana City Museum, where besides the scientific monograph, the main results of two research projects were presented, namely the basic research project “MESTUR – Analysis of territorial and social impacts on the urban tourism and its territorial governance: the cases of Ljubljana and Maribor” and the Horizon 2020 programme funded project titled “SPOT – Innovative social platform for cultural tourism and its potential to enhance Europeanisation”.

In the first project, in addition to the Biotechnical Faculty (University of Ljubljana), which led the project, the Faculty of Economics (UL), the Faculty of Social Sciences (UL) and the Faculty of Arts of the University of Maribor participated. The total value of the project, which ran between July 2019 and June 2022, was 150,000 EUR. Through a mix of qualitative and quantitative research approaches (analysis of tourism statistics, a survey on the spatial behaviour and decision-making of tourists, workshops with representatives of the profession and public institutions, and cartographic analysis), we have identified what solutions spatial planning and tourism management can offer now and what they could offer in the future to mitigate the negative effects of urban tourism and improve the quality of life of local populations.

In the second project, the SPOT project, we have been exploring the topic of cultural tourism with 15 partners from EU countries, Israel and the UK since January 2020. The project is led by Assist. Prof. Dr. Naja Marot, junior researcher David Klepej and researchers Manca Krošelj and Nina Stubičar from the Department of Landscape Architecture.

The diverse team brings a wide range of knowledge and ideas to the project, and ensures close collaboration with local, regional and national stakeholders in order to renew the understanding and treatment of cultural tourism. Researchers are exploring new forms of cultural tourism, identifying opportunities and developing strategies to enable local communities to better exploit the potential of cultural heritage and other cultural offerings in the case study area. Researchers and stakeholders work together to develop policy proposals and use the SPOT-IT geo-information tool to generate knowledge and guidance to help decision-makers and tourism providers.

 Vabimo vas na sklepni dogodek
 raziskovalnega projekta MESTUR z naslovom:
**Analiza in upravljanje prostorskih in družbenih učinkov
 mestnega turizma na primeru Ljubljane, Gradca in Maribora**

 Shranite si datum, **petek, 17. junij 2022,**
 in se nam ob **9.30** pridružite v **Mestnem muzeju Ljubljana.**
Projekt financira Javna agencija za raziskovalno dejavnost Republike Slovenije.

Both research projects have been deeply affected by the covid-19 virus pandemic, which has hit the tourism industry in particular. The impact on urban tourism and its derivatives such as congress, festival, cultural or gastronomy tourism has been particularly negative. As a result, the two projects surveyed various stakeholders in urban tourism in Ljubljana and Maribor to examine their preparedness and response to the pandemic and their views on the development of the tourism sector in the new situation.

In addition to the presentation of the key results of the MESTUR and SPOT projects and the dissemination of the scientific monograph titled "Urban Tourism in Slovenia: Characteristics and Governance", we invited participants from the spatial and tourism sectors to discuss urban tourism in a roundtable discussion titled "New urban tourism in Slovenian cities - towards better integration of spatial planning and tourism?". The panellists were: Simona Pinterič from the Maribor Tourist Board, who has many years of experience in the field of promotion and marketing of urban tourism; Irena Ograjenšek from the Faculty of Economics (UL), who teaches and researches in the field of marketing; Dejan Ristić, who is responsible for the area of tourism infrastructure at Tourism Ljubljana; Miha Bratec from the Faculty of Tourism Studies at the University of Primorska, who presented the SMARTDEST research project,

funded by the Horizon 2020 programme, and Miran Gajšek from the Municipality of Ljubljana, Head of the Department of Urban Planning. After the event, the participants had the opportunity to take a tour titled "Plečnik at a glance" or a guided tour of the museum's permanent exhibition, an experience that made them visitors to the city themselves.

Annual Meeting of the International Geographical Union Commission on Local and Regional Development

SPOT team members attended the Annual Meeting of the International Geographical Union Commission on Local and Regional Development "Sociodemographic change and its impact on territorial development policies" which took place in Cuenca (Spain), between 13 and 15 October 2022. The meeting was organized together with the Spanish Working Group of Local Development, part of the Association of Spanish Geographers (AGE), and the Department of Geography and Spatial Planning of the University of Castilla-La Mancha.

Presentations of SPOT team members:

Ines GRIGORESCU, Bianca MITRICĂ, Irena MOCANU, Monica DUMITRAȘCU, Nicoleta DAMIAN, Paul ȘERBAN, Cristina DUMITRICĂ, Institute of Geography, Romanian Academy, Romania: Challenges of Cultural Tourism in Buzău Carpathians and Sub-Carpathians (Romania). Local Businesses' Perspective.

Tamás HARDI, Centre for Economic and Regional Studies Institute for Regional Studies, Hungary: Analysis of cross-border movements in the Slovak-Hungarian border area during COVID closures

Michael SOFER, Bar Ilan University, Israel: The restructuring of the rural-urban fringe: A case study of Tel-Aviv Metropolitan Area.

Conference for Cultural Tourism in Europe in Krk by the University of Graz

The ECTN's conference was held in October in Krk this year, hereby the University of Graz took the chance to bring in the geographer's point of view, addressing the topic of cultural heritage in peripheral regions within two contributions by Jörn Harfst and Jasmin Sandriester.

2022 Winter School on Digital Cultural Tourism and Diplomacy in Cyprus

On 14 February, Milada Šťastná presented the SPOT project at the 2022 Winter School on Digital Cultural Tourism and Diplomacy in Cyprus. The Winter School is dedicated among other goals to "promoting forms of tourism (cultural, historic, religious, gastronomy, wine, etc.) that go beyond traditional "sun sea and sand", and can verifiably serve as a vehicle of cultural diplomacy".

Current Problems of Tourism Conference

On March 2-3, 2022, the Jihlava Polytechnic College, Department of Tourism, organized the 16th annual international conference Current Problems of Tourism on the topic CRISIS SOLUTIONS FOR TOURISM. The conference focused on the following topics: Destination Management and Marketing; Hospitality; Tourism Research and Best Practices; and Crisis Solutions for Tourism during and after the Coronavirus Time. The SPOT H2020 project was represented by the MENDELU team where Milada Šťastná, along with Antonín Vaishar and Jan Zloch presented the main focus of the SPOT project and the first results out of the Czech case study - Jihomoravský Kraj/The South Moravian region.

Alfred Krogmann, Hilda Kramáreková, Magdaléna Nemčíková and Daša Oremusová held a presentation titled „Dynamics of tourism indicators in Slovakia in the years 2016 – 2020” as well.

Workshop on Cultural and creative industries

On May 23rd, 2022, IGAR team participated in the online Workshop on Cultural and creative industries organised by the Ministry of Development, Public Works and Administration through the Priority Area 3 - Culture, tourism and people contacts within the European Union Strategy for the Danube Region (EUSDR). On this occasion, some of SPOT project results were disseminated within the paper entitled: Linking culture and creativity through SPOT project. Authors: Ines Grigorescu, Bianca Mitrică and Irena Mocanu.

SPOT in America. Participation in the AAG 2022 Conference

On February 28 2022, in the context of the American Association of Geographers' (AAG) Annual Meeting 2022, our SPOT project was presented online in the form of five research papers organized as a session with the title "Landscape and Cultural Tourism. The SPOT EU Project". Theano S. Terkenli (University of the Aegean) and Milada Štastná (Mendel University in Brno) co-organized and co-chaired this session, which was officially recorded and remained accessible to all Conference participants, on the AAG website, till August 29, 2022.

The AAG is the most prestigious and acclaimed scientific geographical organization in the United States, and its annual meetings have been a prized institution for thousands of geographers from the States and from around the world. This year, the meeting, originally organized in New York City, took place in an entirely virtual form, with 3.200 presentations in over 1,000 sessions, 18 networking events and 12 workshops. The SPOT session was sponsored by the following three AAG Specialty Groups: Landscape; European; and Recreation, Tourism and Sports. It consisted of the following papers:

- Landscape for Cultural Tourism: an affair to unfold. Theano S. Terkenli, Marcel Pleijte, Małgorzata Pstrocka-Rak, Giovanna Rech, Milada Štastná, Tijn Rümke and Bas Pedroli.
 - Cultural Tourism after COVID-19: first findings. Milada Štastná, Antonín Vaishar.
 - Worth a visit? Challenges and opportunities for touristic valorization of an industrial heritage landscape - the case of the Styrian Iron Route (Austria). Jasmin Sandriester, Jörn Harfst.
 - Conflicting perceptions of urban landscapes: the case of tourism and housing in Barcelona. Danielle Bishop, Montserrat Pareja-Eastaway & Montserrat Simó Solsona.
 - Piedmont landscapes: cultural resources and visual host/guest encounters in SPOT project. Giovanna Rech, Lorenzo Migliorati.
- The session purported to address research inroads and state-of-the-art insights into the interrelationships between landscape and cultural tourism. It presented theoretical and empirical aspects and advances in this scientific area, with an emphasis on European case study examples, based on research carried out in SPOT.

In the context of rapidly changing rates and globalizing patterns of mobility and consumption, this session aimed to respond to the need for renewed, place-specific, and more in-depth scientific investigation into the sites and attractions sought by cultural tourists and into the role of landscape in visitor experiences. The papers illustrated and elaborated on distinct and critical issues stemming from and revolving around the interface of landscape and cultural tourism, at a time of increasing demand for a variety of broadly accessible tourism/leisure pursuits and activities, as well as concern about sustainable/'green' development for the landscape, for the local societies, and for tourism.

SPOT went all virtual!

The SPOT partners from the University of Graz have presented research results at the Regional Studies 'Regions in Recovery - eFestival2022'. The virtual conference format of the network for regional research took place in March 2022. Jörn Harfst and Jasmin Sandriester from the Department of Geography and Regional Science presented a paper in the tourism session, discussing the role of cultural heritage institutions and digitalisation in regional development, especially in more peripheral regions.

V4 online training

Prof. Milada Šťastná took part in the V4 online training between 28-31 March 2022. The purpose of training was to increase the professional capacity of research managers (RMs) by providing targeted information with added value from Brussels and raising their awareness of the political context of European research and innovation programs and initiatives with special focus on Framework programmes.

Prof. Milada Šťastná presented the SPOT project on Day 3 during the session „Tips and tricks from successful H2020 projects”.

29th Colloquium of the International Geographical Union Commission

The IGAR team attended the 29th Colloquium of the International Geographical Union Commission on the Sustainability of Rural Systems "Necessities and implementations for Sustaining Rural Systems in both Developed and less Developed Environments" held in Cairo & Shebeen-Elkom, Menoufia University Egypt, February 28 - March 4, 2022. During the conference IGAR team presented the paper titled Insights into tourists, residents and businesses perception on cultural tourism. The showcase of a rural area of Buzău Carpathians and Subcarpathians (Romania), authors: Bianca Mitrică, Nicoleta Damian, Ines Grigorescu, Irena Mocanu, Paul-Răzvan Șerban, Monica Dumitrașcu, Cristina Dumitrică.

Other conference and event participations

-50th Annual Conference of Urban Affairs Association (UAA) 2022 (12-14.04.2022.)

Participating partner:

UB: Cultural Tourism as a Means for Renewing Community Engagement in Barcelona: The Case of Sant Pau Recinte Modernista

11th Cultural Routes Annual Advisory Forum, Chania (Crete), Greece

5 - 7 October 2022, University Network for Cultural Routes Studies Meeting.

Participating partner:

UKF: Cultural routes: protection of European values, heritage and dialogue, promotion of SPOT project.

-The Thessalonian Brothers Saints Cyril and Methodius and their Contribution to the Development of European Culture (09-10.05.2022.)

Participating partner:

UKF: European Cultural Route of Saints Cyril and Methodius – Current Perspectives and Future Possibilities in the Czech Republic and Slovakia

-Cyril and Methodius Route - Cultural Route of the Council of Europe (17.05.2022.)

Participating partner:

UKF: European values in relation to the Cyril and Methodius heritage

MESTUR Project Conference (17.06.2022.)

Organising and participating partner:

UL- Naja Marot, David Klepej, Nina Stubičar, Manca Krošelj

-Giovanna Rech, Luca Mori, "Cultural tourism and intangible heritage: the role of Langhe Monferrato and Roero landscape's social representation" in Rethinking Culture and Creativity. The Role of Cultural Heritage in the Green and Digital Transition, Online International Workshop, University of Macerata, 10th-11th November 2022.

29th International Geographical Conference - Geographical aspects of the Central European area – Central Europe in (Post)pandemic period.

20 – 21 October 2022, Nitra, Slovakia

Participating partner:

UKF: Promotion of SPOT project results.

Digital Transformation Summit 24. – 27. 10. 2022, Funchal (Madeira) Participating partner:

UKF: CPU in Nitra – Open Horizons for Cooperation (not only) in Cultural Tourism, promotion of SPOT project results.

-25th International Colloquium on Regional Science (22-24.06.2022.)

Participating partners:

UKF - Oremusová, D., Nemčíková, M., Petrikovičová, L., Kramáreková, H., Krogmann, A.: Development of municipalities in the Nitra Diocese in the context of religious tourism

UKF - Petrikovičová, L., Petrikovič, J., Wittlinger, L.: Covid-19 Pandemic Reflection on Tourism and Tour Operators

-13th Annual International Religious Tourism and Pilgrimage Conference (IRTP) (29.06-02.07.2022.)

Participating partner:

UKF: Potential of the St. Cyril and Methodius Cultural Route for culture tourism development

-AESOP Annual Congress 2022 (25.-29.07.2022.)

Participating partner:

UNIGRAZ: Cultural heritage as a driver of sustainable development in peripheral regions? Observations from Austria

TLU: Cooperation and competition among large industrial sites in heritage tourism

UL - David Klepej: Response of strategic spatial planning to the growth of urban tourism: Case of Central European cities

UL - Nina Stubičar: Spatial analysis as a tool for determining the scope and impact of tourism promotion onto the tourist flow in the cities, example of the City of Ljubljana, Slovenia

-26th Apáczai-days Scientific Conference, Széchenyi István University, Győr, 2022.11.10.

Smahó, Melinda: Cross-border cultural tourism development in the Komárom area.

UL - Manca Krošelj: Place-based tourism: an exploration of new interpretations of cultural tourism

-International Conference on Tourism and Social Research, "Rethinking Tourism, Hospitality and Events for a Better Future" Ukulhas, the Republic of the Maldives (02-05.08.2022.)

Participating partner:

BIU - Shmuel, I., Sofer, M., Amit-Cohen, I., Tchetchik, A., Shiff, S. and Michael, Y.: COVID-19 and the impact on cultural tourism: The case of Beit She'an Valley, Israel,

-61st ERSA Congress (08.23.-26.08.2022.)

Participating partner:

CERS - Eszter Szemerédi: Strengthening the cohesion of cross-border cultural tourism destinations utilising digital instruments in the cross-border region of Komárom-Komárno

-AISRe Conference - Italian Conference on Regional Sciences (Italian session of the Regional Science Association International) (05-07.09.2022.)

Participating partner: UNIVR

-PECSRL 2022 "Living together in European Rural Landscapes" (26.09.-02.10.2022.)

Participating partner:

UAEGEAN - Theano S. Terkenli, Vasiliki Georgoula: „Landscape and Tourism. Looking forward“ Presentation related to the SPOT project's research outcomes. Session Title: „Living together with tourism through a landscape“ perspective organised and chaired by Theano S. Terkenli, Bernadetta Castiglioni and Ewa Skowronek

-6th International Scientific Conference on IT, Tourism, Economics, Management and Agriculture - ITEMA 2022, on 27.10.2022 (online)

Smahó, Melinda: Partnership as a success factor in cross-border cultural tourism development. The case of Komárom.

WORKSHOPS:

Workshops:

-SPOT WorkShop 1: Good Practices of Cultural Tourism and Tourism Culture (03.02.2022.)

Organising partner: WR

-TEXTOUR - Narva Cultural Tourism Strategy Workshop I (23.02.2022.)

Participating partner: TLU

-SPOT WorkShop 2: Suggestions for Golden Rules (03.03.2022.)

Organising partner: UL

-ENHR New Researchers Seminar (11.03.2022.)

Participating and organising partner: UB

-TEXTOUR - Narva Cultural Tourism Strategy Workshop II (25.03.2022.)

Participating partner: TLU

-SPOT WorkShop 3: Cultural tourism and regional development (good practices) (05.04.2022.)

Organising partner: MENDELU

-SPOT WorkShop 4: Cultural tourism and local stakeholders (11-13.05.2022.)

Organising partner: IGAR

-MESTUR project workshop about urban and cultural tourism in Slovenian towns (13.05.2022.)

Organising and participating partner: UL

-JN TIA project workshop in Virštanj, SI (18.05.2022.)

Organising and participating partner: UL

-Working group for the Càtedra Barcelona d'Estudis d'Habitatge (09.06.2022.)

Participating and organising partner: UB

-Syros SPOT Symposium „The cultural and natural heritage of the island of Syros - The Spot project significance“ (13-15.06.2022.)

Hermoupolis, Syros, Greece

Organising and participating partner: UAEGEAN

-Boulouki Organisation of Symposium 'Under the Landscape' (26-29.06.2022.) Santorini and Therassia, Greece

Participating partner: UAEGEAN

-The contribution of innovative and creative tourism to support sustainable local development in the frame of Priority Area 3 - Culture, tourism and people within the European Union Strategy for the Danube Region (EUSDR) – (26.07.2022.)

Participating partner: UNIVR

Participation to events other than a conference or workshop:

-Meeting of Cultural Heritage Site Managers (20.01.2022.)

Organising partner: BIU

-Meeting with Head of a local commerce group to discuss synergies between the SPOT project and local commerce (in conjunction with business survey fieldwork) (26.01.2022.)

Participating partner: UB

-UNESCO Winter School (13-20.02.2022.)

Participating partner: UNIABDN

-The impact of COVID-19 on Cultural Tourism workshop (22.03.2022.)

Participating partner: UNIABDN

-Excursion and roundtable in the case study area of Beit She'an Valley (25-29.04.2022.)

Organising partner: BIU

Participating partner: CERS, IGAR

-Guest lecture/presentation at Central European University: Planning and management of urban tourism in heritage cities (24.05.2022.)

Participating partner: UL – David Klepej

-SmartCulTour Webinar on cultural tourism policies and interventions - State-of-the-art in European cultural tourism policies and practices (20.06.2022.)

Participating partner: UWR, MENDELU, WR, UNIABDN

-Cyril and Methodius journey in the footsteps of St. Cyril and Methodius from Dražoviec via Zobor to Nitra (04.07.2022.)

Organising and participating partner: UKF

-Nitra, Dear Nitra... (Pribina's Festival and Cyril and Methodius Festivities on the Cyril and Methodius Route established by the Council of Europe) (03-05.07.2022.)

Organising and participating partner: UKF

PUBLICATIONS

Peer-reviewed articles

-Bishop, D., Pareja-Eastaway, M., Simó Solsona, M. (2022): The End of 'Business as Usual'? Reimagining Barcelona Tourism After Covid-19, *Journal of Tourism, Culture & Communication* (under publication)

-Horvat, U., Stubičar, N. (2021): Pojavnost in prepoznavnost poglavitnih turističnih znamenitosti in lokacij v Mariboru/Presence and identification of the main tourist attractions and sites in Maribor. *Journal for Geography*, 16 (2), pp. 7-32.

Sandriester ,J., Kern, C., Harfst, J. (2022): The impact of the COVID-19 crisis on tourism development in peripheral areas in Austria, *Tourism, Culture and Communication*

-Kramáreková, H., Petrikovičová, L., Krogmann, A., Grežo, H. (2022): The Pandemic as a Challenge for the Diversification of Tourism, *Tourism Culture and Communications* (under publication) <https://doi.org/10.3727/109830422X16600594683409>

-Sofer, M., Shmuel, I., Amit-Cohen, I., Tchetchik, A., Shiff, S., Michael, Y. (2022): COVID-19 and the impact on cultural tourism: The case of Beit She'an Valley, Israel, *Tourism, Culture & Communication* (under publication)

-Terkenli T. S. and Georgoula, V. Tourism and Cultural Sustainability: Views and Prospects from Cyclades, Greece. *Sustainability*. 2022; 14(1):307. <https://doi.org/10.3390/su14010307>

-Terkenli, T. S. and Georgoula, V. (2022): The COVID-19 pandemic in the Cyclades: patterns and prospects in cultural tourism, *Tourism, Culture and Communication* (under publication)

-Vaishar, A., Šťastná, M. (2022): Impact of the COVID-19 pandemic on rural tourism in Czechia Preliminary considerations, *Current Issues in Tourism*, 25 (2), pp. 187-191.

-Vaishar, A., Šťastná, M., Kramáreková, H. (2022): Moravian-Slovak Borderland: Possibilities for Rural Development, *Sustainability*, 14 (6), 3381.

-Wallace, C., Garrison, S., Chen, J., Shaddock, J. (2022): COVID and Cultural Tourism, *Tourism Culture and Communications* (under publication)

Conference papers, monographs, book chapters:

-Krogmann, A., Kramáreková, H., Nemčíková, M., Oremusová, D. (2022): Dynamics of tourism indicators in Slovakia in the years 2016 - 2020. *Proceedings of the 16th International Conference Topical issues of tourism*, pp. 176-185.

-Marot, N., Uršič, M. (ed.), Horvat, U., Klepej, D., Krošelj, M., Ograjenšek, I., Stubičar, N. (2022): Mestni turizem v Sloveniji: značilnosti in upravljanje/Urban tourism in Slovenia: Characteristics and governance. Univerza v Ljubljani, Biotehniška fakulteta, Ljubljana https://www.bf.uni-lj.si/mma/MESTUR_knjiga_KON__NA_digitalna_verzija.pdf/2022071513510556/?m=1657885866

-Oremusová, D., Nemčíková, M., Petrikovičová, L., Kramáreková, H., Krogmann, A. (2022): Development of municipalities in the Nitra Diocese in the context of religious tourism. Proceedings of the 25th International Colloquium on Regional Sciences, pp. 391-399. <https://doi.org/10.5817/CZ.MUNI.P280-0068-2022-48>

-Petrikovičová, L., Petrikovič, J., Wittlinger, L. (2022): Covid-19 Pandemic Reflection on Tourism and Tour Operators. Proceedings of the 25th International Colloquium on Regional Sciences, pp. 320-328. <https://doi.org/10.5817/CZ.MUNI.P280-0068-2022-39>

-Terkenli, T. S., and Georgoula, V. (2022). Local Perspectives on Cultural Tourism and Cultural Sustainability: The Case of the Cyclades, Greece, Chapter 15, Handbook of Research on Cultural Tourism and Sustainability, pp.323-348, IGI Global, DOI: 10.4018/978-1-7998-9217-5.ch015

L. (2022). Potential of the European Cultural Route of St. Cyril and Methodius for the development of cultural tourism. In. International Journal of Religious Tourism and Pilgrimage (in print)

-Ivanič, P. (2022). Relics of St. Constantine-Cyril in Slovakia. In Konštantínove listy [Constantine's Letters] 15/2, 106-126.

-Krogmann, A., Kramáreková, H., Petrikovičová, L., Grežo, H. (2022). Remeselné pivovary na Slovensku a ich potenciál pre rozvoj cestovného ruchu / Craft breweries in Slovakia and their potential for tourism development (poster and abstract). In: Česká a slovenská geografie: mezinárodní tradicí a mezinárodní relevancí: sborník abstraktů, 06.09.2022-08.09.2022, Olomouc/ Fiedor, D., Minxová, P., Smolová, I. - Olomouc: UP, 2022. ISBN 978-80-244-6178-6, s. 190,

Reports:

-MENDELU (2022): D5.5 Policy Report 1. <https://zenodo.org/record/6337218#YrXaJXZBw2w>

-UNIABDN (2022): D2.2 Summary Report on Stakeholder Involvement. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6337207>

-UNIABDN (2022): D2.3 Summary Report of impact evaluations of cultural tourism on target areas. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6674130>

SPOT IN THE MEDIA

La ricerca continua

The SPOT project and Italian case study have been presented in the format La RICERCA continua all'Università di Verona nonostante l'emergenza Covid that is curated by the University of Verona Communication team to show how the research is going to be carried on, despite and through the pandemic. <https://youtu.be/CEMj8BjTNm0>

Radio Interview.

04.06.2021, Radio interview at FM Radio Athens 98,4 with Professor Theano S. Terkenli. Topic 'The significance of cultural tourism in Greece and beyond. The aims and objectives of the H2020 SPOT project and the potential uses of the innovative SPOT IT TOOL'

YouTube live streaming

of the SPOT Symposium 'The cultural and natural heritage of the island of Syros - The Spot project significance' (13-15.06.2022) Hermoupolis, Syros, Greece <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=L7GR47KtKAE>

Press Release. 10.06.2022, Press release in local (Cycladic) press, to announce the organization of the Spot Project Symposium in Syros, 15th June 2022.

Podcast of the University of Graz team

CULTURAL TOURISM POST COVID-19

Innovative solutions during the pandemic and the way to a more resilient cultural tourism

The COVID-19 pandemic, as well as related social isolation and travel restrictions, has had a devastating effect on cultural tourism. However after restrictions on travel have been lifted tourism started to recover as well. According to Eurostat nights spent in EU tourist accommodation increased by 27% in 2021. This brought the total to 1.8 billion, which was still 37% less than in 2019, before COVID-19 with Eurostat stating that the figures are "far less dramatic" than the difference between 2019 and 2020, when tourism in the EU halved. (World Economic Forum, 2022 <https://www.weforum.org/agenda/2022/03/europe-tourism-has-slow-pandemic-recovery/>). Restarting cultural tourism is a major concern for governments around the world, and the UNWTO Ethics, Culture and Social Responsibility Department in collaboration with its international partners prepared some recommendations for restarting cultural tourism. According to their recommendations there could be a shift from quantity to quality. Tourism and culture should work together to recover by aligning resilience policies, new priorities with new measurement values, and tailor-made marketing strategies.

Diversification is an important aspect, by customizing their cultural offer, governments, destinations and cultural industries can have a more international outreach and local communities' role will be essential in embracing first visitor flows, with precautions. Innovation in SMEs, cooperatives and creative economy will be needed for the recovery of cultural tourism, especially for the empowerment of women, youth & indigenous peoples. The shift from informal towards formal economy will benefit many communities and destinations. Accessibility of cultural facilities, products and services should be advanced to cater better to the needs of persons with disabilities, seniors and families with small children, locals & visitors alike (UNWTO, 2022 <https://www.unwto.org/cultural-tourism-covid-19>).

Roll-up, leaflets and more dissemination materials:
<http://www.spotprojecth2020.eu/media-and-downloads>

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www.SPOTprojectH2020.eu

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